

Vibrational communication and mating behaviour of the psyllid *Bactericera cockerelli*

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An insect pest reliant on vibrational signals for mate finding can potentially be manipulated by means of mechanical stimuli, in order to both monitor and control the target species populations in the field. This strategy could be used to manage the tomato potato psyllid, *Bactericera cockerelli*, which is a major pest of various solanaceous plants. To assess the role of vibrational communication in pair formation, we therefore conducted a series of bioassays and recorded the emitted vibrations using a laser Doppler vibrometer from a leaf surface. On a potted bell pepper leaf, we released either individuals of a male (n=56) and a female (n=37) or pairs (n=62). A pre-recorded vibrational signal was transmitted to the leaf using a mini-shaker to evaluate whether the male (n=19) could be attracted towards the source point. We described the pair formation process and characterised both the male and female vibrational signals associated with mating. Mating signals were mostly initiated by the male (84%) and a vibrational duet was then established with the females that responded to their call (57%). During the duet, the male searched for the female, which remained stationary on the leaf. Mating was achieved (76%) if the male could continue to elicit the female reply and use her vibrations as cues to localise her. In a second experiment, the playback transmission of pre-recorded signals led most males to reach the source point, and to remain for a long period of time on the stimulated area, while fewer males of the silent control group walked towards the mini-shaker. We concluded that *B. cockerelli* uses species-specific vibrational signals to identify and localise a suitable mate. For this reason, we hypothesize that the mating behaviour of this species is likely to be vulnerable to manipulation by means of vibrations. More research will be conducted to improve the attractiveness of the stimulus, in order to develop a mechanical monitoring and/or control technique.

Conference section

I want to present this oral contribution in the section:

	Emerging pathogens of forestry
x	<i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> and psyllid vectors